

ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF FAMILY PLANNING EXTENSION CENTER IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

One of the world's biggest challenges today is the rapid population growth. The government of Indonesia has implemented family planning (FP) programs to regulate Indonesia's population growth. This study aims to analyze the factors that affect the organizational performance of the FP extension center. This research is quantitative. Sampling using stratified random sampling technique with a total sample of 430 samples. Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) analysis is used, which aims to examine several dependent relationships partially and simultaneously. There is a positive and significant influence of the utilization of information and communication technology, individual characteristics, organizational communication climate in the FP extension center, communication satisfaction of field line officers, and effectiveness of organizational communication in the FP extension center on the organizational performance of the FP extension center simultaneously. The result of this study provides an overview of how to improve the organizational performance of the FP extension center.

Keywords: Effectiveness of Organizational Communication, FP Extension Center, Organizational Performance, PLS-SEM.

INTRODUCTION

One of the biggest challenges facing the world today is rapid population growth. Lutz et al. (2001) revealed that the world's population will peak this century. Cleland (2013) states that population increase in the world is inevitable, and its implications for human well-being and the environment. Since 1970, the Government of Indonesia has implemented family planning (FP) programs to regulate Indonesia's population growth. Through childbirth arrangements, the FP program focuses family expenses on education and health costs to improve the quality of competitive human resources (Sarmita, 2017). Cleland et al. (2011) stated that the FP Program is a cost-effective health prevention service effort. The FP program in Indonesia is controlled by the FP extension center (Hakim, 2018), so it is essential to examine the performance of the FP extension center. The performance of the organization is formed from the expertise of individual members of the organization, willingness to work by the agreement, and hope for a better future (Agustina et al., 2019), while the organizational performance of the FP extension

center in this study, one of which is shown by the quality of service to the community as a partner or client of the FP extension center organization. Adlen et al. (2018) revealed that the success of an organization can be measured by the level of satisfaction felt by partners or clients of the organization. Tristante et al. (2023) explained that crucial for decision-makers to boost business performance.

Hoai et al. (2022) concluded that internal control systems (ICS) can increase the intensity of innovation and have an effect on organizational performance. In contrast to the study, this study will examine the influence of the use of information and communication technology, individual characteristics, communication climate, and communication satisfaction, as well as the effectiveness of organizational communication on organizational performance at the FP extension center. Wiratama et al. (2017) found that information technology has a positive and significant influence on performance; in this case, the dimensions of forming information technology are closely related to the ability to use information technology. Suryani and Foeh (2018) stated that organizational performance is achieved if tasks or work are carried out effectively and efficiently by individuals who are members of the organization. Research Kosasih et al. (2014) recognize the critical role played by organizational communication climate in the development of organizational performance. Fefni (2017) revealed that communication satisfaction has an important role in improving performance because communication satisfaction is satisfaction with information, media, and relationships in organizations. Fefni (2017) further concluded that the variable of organizational communication effectiveness has a positive and significant effect on performance through communication satisfaction.

Based on these various descriptions, this research will fill at least 2 (two) research gaps, namely: *first*, at the theoretical level, this study formulates factors that affect the organizational performance of FP extension centers. *Second*, on a practical level, this study provides strategic recommendations for the development of FP extension center organizational performance through factors that affect it. This research was conducted in Cianjur Regency and Indramayu Regency, West Java Province, Indonesia, to analyze the factors that affect the organizational performance of the FP extension center. The selection of research sites was based on the consideration that both locations already have FP extension centers in all sub-districts, which means that both local governments have high commitment and attention to the FP program.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Robbins (2005) states that the organizational structure is formed so that there is division, grouping, and coordination of work tasks. Furthermore, Robbins (2005) states that the concept of chain of command states to whom members of organizations and groups report the results of their work. Alfian et al. (2021) revealed that in the organizational structure of the FP extension center, there is a head of the FP extension center who has the main duties and functions, namely leading, planning, organizing, implementing, controlling, coordinating the FP Program development and control activity plan at the sub-district level. Referring to the

concept of chain of command, the members of the organization in the FP extension center report all their work to the head of the FP extension center.

Budiana et al. (2015) revealed that information and communication technology includes two aspects, namely, aspects of information technology and aspects of communication technology. The difference between information technology and communication technology is that information technology is matters related to information management, which includes the creation of information sources, maintenance of information channels, selection and transmission of information, selective receipt of information, storage, and tracing of information, and the use of information, while communication technology is matters related to the use of tools to process and transfer data from devices from one device to another. Communication technology is a technological device consisting of hardware, software, processes, and systems used to assist the communication process.

Individual characteristics are inherent characteristics of each field line officer who is a member of the organization in the FP extension center. According to Sumarwan (2011), the concept of subculture is closely related to demography. Demographics can describe the characteristics of a population. Quoting Suparyanto's opinion, Adi et al. (2017) stated that socioeconomic status is a condition inherent in a person or a society in terms of socio-economy, such conditions as income level, asset ownership, and so on. The individual characteristic in the ability dimension (Karim, 2019) is the ability to complete the work charged.

Denison (1996) states that organizational culture and climate are fundamentally different, and there is no overlapping phenomenon between the two. Organizational climate is defined as situations within an organization that relate to the behavior, feelings, and thoughts of members of the organization. In line with this opinion, Schneider et al. (2013) stated that organizational climate is briefly defined as the meaning attached to a person's interrelated experiences they have at work. Organizational culture is briefly defined as the basic assumptions about the world and the values that guide life in organizations. Albrecht (1979) revealed that the nature of communication systems in organizations is an important factor in shaping the perception of organizational climate.

Ahsanul (2013) explained that the communication climate is different from the organizational climate in that the communication climate involves the perception of messages and message-related events that occur in the organization. Furthermore, Ahsanul (2013) revealed that the organizational communication climate is a metaphor taken from the physical climate. Just as weather creates a physical climate for a region, the way people react to organizational aspects creates a climate of communication. In other words, the communication climate is a composite of perceptions based on macro-evaluations, communicative events, human behavior, employees' responses to each other, expectations, interpersonal conflicts, and opportunities for growth within the organization.

Down and Hazen (1977) stated that communication satisfaction is individual satisfaction that affects aspects of communication in the organizational environment. In line with this opinion, as quoted from Redding, Arifin (2005) explained that communication satisfaction is the overall

level of satisfaction felt by individuals in their communication environment. Satisfaction indicates an individual's affective reaction to a desired outcome that comes from communication within the organization.

Damayanti and Efrina (2021) stated that the effectiveness of organizational communication is something that shows the quality of achieving the desired results and communication activities in an organization. The effectiveness of organizational communication is very important for the smooth and effective communication processes as a whole. According to Devito (1997), communication between people in organizations will be effective if it contains the following characteristics: (1) the existence of support, namely an open situation between communicators and communicants so that they have the same understanding and mutual understanding; (2) there is an openness created between the communicator and the communicant so that the message can be conveyed openly without fear or shame; (3) the presence of empathy, so that the communicator projects himself towards the communicant, ultimately influencing the communicant's attitude; (4) equality, to create closer communication between communicators and communicants; (5) There is a positive feeling, to create a conducive communication situation between the communicator and the communicant, in the end, the communicant will act according to the message conveyed by the communicator.

Performance is the result of the work of individuals or groups in an organization that can be measured according to the responsibilities given to the individual or group (Sinaga et al., 2020). Aditama and Widowati (2017) stated that organizational performance is the ability of the organization to carry out every task mandated to the organization to achieve the goals, objectives, vision, and mission of the organization that has been determined. Organizational performance not only focuses on achieving results or goals but also emphasizes the implementation process and resources to achieve its goals. Syamsuddin and Lisdawati (2020) used 5 (five) performance indicators to determine organizational performance in Pandeglang Regency, namely: (1) productivity, (2) service quality, (3) responsiveness, (4) responsibility, and (5) accountability.

METHODOLOGY

This research is descriptive explanatory, which is research that aims to describe, evaluate, and explain the relationship between research variables through hypothesis testing (Singarimbun and Effendi, 2006). This study used statistical analysis and survey design, with a time horizon once in a period (cross-sectional studies) conducted based on primary data using questionnaire instruments and supported by available secondary data. According to Creswell (2020), the world-view of quantitative research is positivistic, where quantitative research tests a theory by detailing specific hypotheses and then collecting data to support or refute these hypotheses. Based on this, the paradigm used in this study is positivistic. The population of field line officers was taken from 10 FP extension centers that were sampled, with a total field line officers population of 930 people. This study determined the number of samples using the Slovin formula (Setiawan, 2007) so that a total sample of 430 samples was obtained. Field line officers' sampling techniques use stratified random sampling techniques. Namely, sampling

involves a stratification process based on various factors, and it is known that a stratum is homogeneous from within but heterogeneous with other strata, then, random samples are taken from each stratum (Sekaran and Bougie, 2010).

The data used in this study are primary data and secondary data. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2010), primary data is information obtained by researchers from respondents using instruments which are used to achieve specific research goals. Primary data collection will be carried out from January to June 2023, obtained through questionnaire instruments. The questionnaire instrument trial was carried out on 30 field line officers at the FP extension center who were not research samples and were located in the Cianjur Regency in November 2022. The choice of the location of the instrument trial is the location because it has the criteria of respondents that are relatively the same as the object of research. Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) analysis is used, which aims to examine several dependent relationships partially and simultaneously, using available data to estimate path relationships in a model (Hair et al., 2014). Ghazali and Latan (2020) stated that PLS-SEM is an analytical method used to explain the presence or absence of relationships between latent variables (prediction) and can also be used to confirm theories. This study used SmartPLS 3.0 software for PLS-SEM testing.

Based on the results of validity and reliability tests, it is known that this research instrument is generally valid and reliable. The value of instrument validity is in the range of 0.417 to 0.997 (significant in α 0.05 and 0.01), meaning that the measuring instrument used is valid or trusted to measure the variables used in this study. The reliability value also indicates a reliable value, this is indicated by Cronbach's alpha value that exceeds the minimum value set at 0.600, which is in the range of 0.627 to 0.996, which means that this research instrument is reliable or reliable. Thus, all variables on the research instrument show valid and reliable results, meaning that the instrument can be used further to obtain precise and accurate field data.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Structural model analysis with PLS-SEM analysis using SmartPLS 3.0 software has resulted in a structural model relationship path for the organizational performance of the FP extension center. The determining factors that can affect the organizational performance of the FP extension center are information and communication technology, individual characteristics, organizational communication climate, communication satisfaction, and organizational communication effectiveness in the FP extension center. Partially, a t-test was conducted to see the effect of these variables on the organizational performance of the FP extension center. The following are the partial test results of the determinants of FP extension center organizational performance:

a. The effect of the utilization of information and communication technology on the organizational performance of the FP extension center

Based on PLS-SEM analysis, it is known that the effect of the utilization of information and communication technology on the organizational performance of the FP extension center can

be written in the form of the following equation: organizational performance of FP extension center = $(-0.047 \times \text{the utilization of information and communication technology}) + \text{error}$. This model explains that the variable utilization of information and communication technology has an influence of -0.047 standard deviations on the organizational performance of the FP extension center, which means that a change of one standard deviation in the variable of the utilization of information and communication technology will increase the organizational performance of FP extension center variable by -0.047 standard deviations.

Hypothesis testing (with $\alpha=0.01$) to determine the direct effect of variables in the use of information and communication technology on the performance of FP extension center organizations partially as follows:

H0: $\delta_1 \leq 0$: There is no positive and significant effect of the utilization of information and communication technology on the organizational performance of the FP extension center partially.

H1: $\delta_1 > 0$: There is a positive and significant influence of the utilization of information and communication technology on the organizational performance of the FP extension center, partially

Testing the hypothesis uses t-test statistics (see Table 1). The results of hypothesis testing show that the influence of the variable of the utilization of information and communication technology on the organizational performance of the FP extension center variable is negative by 0.047, with a very small influence. With the t-count value of 1.285, which is smaller than the t-table value (1.648), it can be concluded that H0 is accepted, meaning that there is no positive and significant influence of the utilization of information and communication technology on the organizational performance of the FP extension center partially. In line with the results of this study, Angelina and Gultom (2014) stated that the utilization of information and communication technology in micro-scale businesses negatively affects their performance.

b. The influence of individual characteristics of field line officers on the organizational performance of the FP extension center

Based on PLS-SEM analysis, it is known that the influence of individual characteristics of field line officers on the organizational performance of the FP extension center can be written in the form of the following equation: organizational performance of FP extension center = $(0.104 \times \text{individual characteristics of field line officers}) + \text{error}$. This model explains that the variable individual characteristics of field line officers have an influence of 0.104 standard deviations on the organizational performance of the FP extension center, which means that a change of one standard deviation in the individual characteristic variables of field line officers will increase the variable organizational performance of the FP extension center by 0.104 standard deviations.

Hypothesis testing (with $\alpha=0.01$) to determine the direct effect of individual characteristic variables of field line officers on the organizational performance of the FP extension center partially as follows:

H0: $\delta_1 \leq 0$: There is no positive and significant influence of the individual characteristics of field line officers on the organizational performance of the FP extension center partially.

H1: $\delta_1 > 0$: There is a positive and significant influence of the individual characteristics of field line officers on the organizational performance of FP extension centers partially.

Testing the hypothesis uses t-test statistics (see Table 1). The results of hypothesis testing show that the influence of individual characteristic variables of field line officers on the organizational performance of FP extension center variables is positive by 0.104 with a fairly small influence. The t-count value of 0.943, which is smaller than the t-table value (1.648), it can be concluded that H0 is accepted, meaning that there is no positive and significant influence of the individual characteristics of field line officers on the organizational performance of FP extension centers partially. This result is contrary to the findings of Sukmawati et al. (2020), which concluded that individual characteristics partially have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Agreeing with the results of this study, Linda et al. (2021) prove that there is no influence of age, which is an indicator of individual characteristics, on the performance of health workers. This result means that employee performance is not determined in real terms by the age factor of the employee concerned. This result rejects the assumption that the higher the age of the employee, the higher the employee's performance because younger and more capable employees can have high performance. Older employees have experience, work ethic, and commitment to the quality of their work.

Linda et al. (2021) also proved that there is no significant effect of length of work on the performance of health workers. This result rejects the argument that the longer the working life, the higher the employee performance. Employees who have had a long working period tend to experience saturation of work routines. Efforts to improve the performance of employees who have a long service period can be done through increasing employee capacity, for example, by attending training activities or seminars to obtain the latest information and knowledge.

c. The effect of organizational communication climate in the FP extension center on organizational performance of the FP extension center

Based on PLS-SEM analysis, it is known that the effect of organizational communication climate in FP extension center on organizational performance of FP extension center can be written in the form of the following equation: organizational performance of FP extension center = $(0.065 \times \text{organizational communication climate in FP extension center}) + \text{error}$. This model explains that the organizational communication climate variable in the FP extension center has an influence of 0.065 standard deviations on the organizational performance of the FP extension center, which means that a change of one standard deviation in the organizational

communication climate variable in the FP extension center will increase the organizational performance of FP extension center variable by 0.065 standard deviations.

Hypothesis testing (with $\alpha=0.01$), to determine the direct effect of organizational communication climate variables in the FP extension center on organizational performance of the FP extension center partially as follows:

H0: $\delta_1 \leq 0$: There is no positive and significant influence of the organizational communication climate in the FP extension center on the organizational performance of the FP extension center partially

H1: $\delta_1 > 0$: There is a positive and significant influence of the organizational communication climate in the FP extension center on the organizational performance of the FP extension center partially

Testing the hypothesis uses t-test statistics (see Table 1). The results of hypothesis testing showed that the influence of organizational communication climate variables in FP extension center on organizational performance of FP extension center variables was positive by 0.065 with very little influence. The t-count value of 1.385 which is smaller than the t-table value (1.648), it can be concluded that H0 is accepted meaning that there is no positive and significant influence of the organizational communication climate in the FP extension center on the organizational performance of the FP extension center partially. This result is in line with the findings of Prasetyo et al. (2022) which concluded that there is a low relationship between organizational communication climate and employee performance.

d. The effect of communication satisfaction of field line officers on the organizational performance of the FP extension center

Based on PLS-SEM analysis, it is known that the effect of field line officers' communication satisfaction on the organizational performance of FP extension center can be written in the form of the following equation: organizational performance of FP extension center = $(0.227 \times \text{field line officers communication satisfaction}) + \text{error}$. This model explains that the variable of field line officers' communication satisfaction has an influence of 0.227 standard deviations on the organizational performance of the FP extension center, which means that a change of one standard deviation in the field line officers' communication satisfaction variable will increase the organizational performance of FP extension center variable by 0.227 standard deviations.

Testing the influence hypothesis (with $\alpha=0.01$), to determine the direct effect of the variable of communication satisfaction of field line officers on the organizational performance of the FP extension center partially as follows:

H0: $\delta_1 \leq 0$: There is no positive and significant effect of communication satisfaction of field line officers on the organizational performance of the FP extension center partially

H1: $\delta_1 > 0$: There is a positive and significant influence of communication satisfaction of field line officers on the organizational performance of the FP extension center partially

Testing the hypothesis uses t-test statistics (see Table 1). The results of hypothesis testing showed that the influence of communication satisfaction of the field line officers variable on the organizational performance of the FP extension center variable was positive by 0.227 with a large influence. The t-count value of 3.419 which is greater than the t-table value (1.648), it can be concluded that H₀ is rejected meaning that there is a positive and significant effect of communication satisfaction of field line officers on the organizational performance of the FP extension center partially. In agreement with the results of this study, Riyantini and Triyono (2016) and Arifin (2005) also concluded that the variable of communication satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

e. The effect of organizational communication effectiveness in FP extension center on organizational performance of FP extension center

Based on PLS-SEM analysis, it is known that the effect of organizational communication effectiveness in the FP extension center on the organizational performance of the FP extension center can be written in the form of the following equation: organizational performance of FP extension center = (0.506 × organizational communication effectiveness in FP extension center) + *error*. This model explains that the variable of organizational communication effectiveness in the FP extension center has an effect of 0.506 standard deviations on the organizational performance of the FP extension center, which means that a change of one standard deviation in organizational communication effectiveness in the FP extension center will increase the organizational performance of FP extension center variables of 0.506 standard deviations.

Hypothesis testing (with $\alpha=0.01$), to determine the direct effect of organizational communication effectiveness variables in the FP extension center on organizational performance of the FP extension center partially as follows:

H₀: $\delta_1 \leq 0$: There is no positive and significant effect of the effectiveness of organizational communication in the FP extension center on the organizational performance of the FP extension center partially

H₁: $\delta_1 > 0$: There is a positive and significant effect of the effectiveness of organizational communication in the FP extension center on the organizational performance of the FP extension center partially

Testing the hypothesis uses t-test statistics (see Table 1). The results of hypothesis testing showed that the influence of the organizational communication effectiveness variable in the FP extension center on the organizational performance of the FP extension center variable was positive by 0.506 with a large influence. The t-count value of 7.459 is greater than the t-table value (1.648), so it can be concluded that H₀ rejected means that there is a positive and significant effect of organizational communication effectiveness in the FP extension center on the organizational performance of the FP extension center partially. These findings confirm the findings of Darmadi (2021), who states that there is a positive and significant influence on the effectiveness of communication on employee performance.

Table 11: Partial test of factors affecting organizational performance of FP extension center

Latent variables	Coefficient Value	t-count	t-table	p-value	Description
the utilization of information and communication technology → organizational performance of FP extension center	-0,047	1,285	1,648	0,200	Not significant
individual characteristics of field line officers → organizational performance of FP extension center	0,104	0,943	1,648	0,346	Not significant
organizational communication climate in FP extension center → organizational performance of FP extension center	0,065	1,385	1,648	0,167	Not significant
communication satisfaction of field line officers → organizational performance of FP extension center	0,227	3,419	1,648	0,001**	Significant
organizational communication effectiveness in FP Extension Center → Organizational performance of FP Extension Center	0,506	7,459	1,648	0,000**	Significant

(Source: author's work)

Description: *Significant at $\alpha=0,05$ dan **Significant at $\alpha=0,01$

In addition to partial tests, simultaneous tests were also carried out to determine the utilization of influence of information and communication technology, individual characteristics of field line officers, organizational communication climate in the FP extension center, communication satisfaction of field line officers, and the effectiveness of organizational communication in the FP extension center on the organizational performance of the FP extension center together or simultaneously, tested with hypotheses (with $\alpha=0.05$ and 0.01) as follows:

- H0: $\gamma_1; \gamma_5=0$: There is no positive and significant influence of the utilization of information and communication technology, individual characteristics of field line officers, organizational communication climate in the FP extension center, communication satisfaction of field line officers, and effectiveness of organizational communication in the FP extension center on the organizational performance of FP extension center simultaneously
- H1: $\gamma_1; \gamma_5 \neq 0$: There is a positive and significant influence of the utilization of information and communication technology, individual characteristics of field line officers, organizational communication climate in the FP extension center, communication satisfaction of field line officers, and effectiveness of organizational communication in the FP extension center on the organizational performance of FP extension center simultaneously

Testing the hypothesis uses t-test statistics (see Table 2). The t-test used is related to the R-Square coefficient of determination (R^2). Based on the calculated t value of 16.042 which is greater than the table t of 1.648, it can be concluded that there is a positive and significant influence of the utilization of information and communication technology, individual characteristics of field line officers, organizational communication climate in FP extension center, communication satisfaction of field line officers and effectiveness of organizational communication in FP extension center on organizational performance of FP extension center simultaneously.

Based on the value of the R-Square coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.561 (see Table 2), it means that changes that occur in organizational performance of FP extension center variables can be explained by changes that occur in the variables of the utilization of information and communication technology, individual characteristics of field line officers, organizational communication climate in FP extension center, communication satisfaction of field line officers and organizational communication effectiveness in FP extension center by 56.1%, and organizational performance of FP extension center variables can be explained by other factors not included in the model at 43.9%. These results explain that the organizational performance of the FP extension center can be largely explained by the utilization of information and communication technology, individual characteristics of field line officers, organizational communication climate in the FP extension center, communication satisfaction of field line officers, and organizational communication effectiveness in FP extension center and the other small part is formed by other factors beyond those variables.

Table 2: Simultaneous test of factors affecting organizational performance of FP extension center

R-Square (R^2)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	t-count	t-table	p-value	Description
0,561	0,035	16,042	1.648	0,000**	Significant

(Source: author's work)

Description: *Significant at $\alpha=0,05$ dan **Significant at $\alpha=0,01$

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Partially, the utilization of information and communication technology, individual characteristics, and organizational communication climate in the FP extension center do not have a significant effect on the organizational performance of the FP extension center, and there is a positive and significant influence of communication satisfaction of field line officers and organizational communication effectiveness in FP extension center on organizational performance of FP extension center. Simultaneously, there is a positive and significant influence of the utilization of information and communication technology, individual characteristics, organizational communication climate in the FP extension center, communication satisfaction of field line officers, and effectiveness of organizational

communication in the FP extension center on organizational performance of the FP extension center.

At the academic level, this study produces a structural model of the organizational performance of FP extension centers, and based on the findings that organizational performance is formed by other factors outside the variables that have not been included in the model, further studies are needed with a broader object of research to observe other factors that can support organizational performance.

At the practical level, to improve the organizational performance of the FP extension center, it is necessary to formulate the concept of coaching and organizational development of the FP extension center by taking into account the dominant factors that influence the creation of a good communication climate, increasing communication satisfaction of field line officers, and increasing the effectiveness of organizational communication at the FP extension center.

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